

A numerical methodology for detection of impact damage using natural frequency

Zhihong Liang

Karthik Ram Ramakrishnan

Zhifang Zhang

Antonio Pellegrino

Motivation

bird strike

- Impact loading during service life causes damage
- Delamination, matrix cracking and fibre failure

Forward problem

- Known location, size and interface of damage
- Evaluate change in natural frequencies

Zhang Z et al.. Vibration-based assessment of delaminations in FRP composite plates. Composites Part B: Engineering. 2018 Jul 1;144:254-66.

Inverse problem

- Predict location, size and interface of damage from frequency shifts

He M et al. A comparison of machine learning algorithms for assessment of delamination in fiber-reinforced polymer composite beams. Structural Health Monitoring. 2021

Impact modelling in Abaqus

Results of impact model

In-built 2D-Hashin model

3D-Hashin model as VUMAT

Validation of impact model

Pham D C, Lua J, Sun H, et al. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2020, 54(4): 449-462.

Time history force of different models.

Delamination damage for different energies

Delamination mapping

Mode shapes of undamaged plate

ODB: o-cos-49-fre-cffc.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-4 Tue Apr 07 14:46:21 GMT+01:00 2020
Step: Step-1
Mode 1: Value = 9.2669E+07 Freq = 1533.0 (cycles/time)
Primary Var: U, Magnitude
Deformed Var: U, Deformation Scale Factor: +1.500e+01

Mode 1

ODB: o-cos-49-fre-cffc.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-4 Tue Apr 07 14:46:21 GMT+01:00 2020
Step: Step-1
Mode 2: Value = 1.59175E+09 Freq = 2008.0 (cycles/time)
Primary Var: U, Magnitude
Deformed Var: U, Deformation Scale Factor: +1.500e+01

Mode 2

ODB: o-cos-49-fre-cffc.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-4 Tue Apr 07 14:46:21 GMT+01:00 2020
Step: Step-1
Mode 3: Value = 5.74929E+08 Freq = 3816.2 (cycles/time)
Primary Var: U, Magnitude
Deformed Var: U, Deformation Scale Factor: +1.500e+01

Mode 3

ODB: o-cos-49-fre-cffc.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-4 Tue Apr 07 14:46:21 GMT+01:00 2020
Step: Step-1
Mode 4: Value = 6.17946E+08 Freq = 3956.0 (cycles/time)
Primary Var: U, Magnitude
Deformed Var: U, Deformation Scale Factor: +1.500e+01

Mode 4

ODB: o-cos-49-fre-cffc.odb Abaqus/Standard 6.14-4 Tue Apr 07 14:46:21 GMT+01:00 2020
Step: Step-1
Mode 5: Value = 3.64862E+08 Freq = 4600.5 (cycles/time)
Primary Var: U, Magnitude
Deformed Var: U, Deformation Scale Factor: +1.500e+01

Mode 5

Mode shapes of damaged plate

3J Impact

Mode 1

Mode 2

Mode 3

Mode 4

Mode 5

16J Impact

Effect of damage on natural frequency

- Frequency shift in different modes are not the same
- Non-linear response

Summary

Impact loading causes complex damage modes

Vibration based SHM uses frequency shifts

Forward vs Inverse problem

Numerical model with delamination mapping

Training of Machine Learning algorithms

Future work on experimental validation of frequency shifts

Fig.6. Frequency shift diagram of finite element model

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